

DRAFT KII Guide Hospital Administrators

Introduction to be read after informed consent is obtained

Hello, my name is _____ and I will be interviewing you. This interview will take approximately one hour.

The reason for conducting this interview is to hear about your thoughts, opinions, and observations about providing care to babies in the SNCU. I will be asking specifically about the barriers and facilitators to providing the best care for babies, including questions about equipment in the SNCU.

With your permission I would like to audio record our conversation; however, your name and other identifying information will not be recorded.

Do you have any questions before I start?

YES

NO

Interviewer's name: _____

Date: _____

Start time: _____ End time: _____

Duration: _____ (min)

Socio-demographics

- 1) What is your age?
- 2) What is your gender?
- 3) What are your qualifications?
- 4) What is your total years of experience in your profession?
- 5) How long have you served as the hospital administrator?

Patient and Unit Characteristics

- 6) What kind of patients visit your SNCU? Below poverty line or above poverty line, gender, in-born, out-born?
- 7) What are the reasons that a baby would be admitted to the SNCU? (Probe: clinical reasons, underweight, infection, birth asphyxia)

Challenges

- 1) Do you have the appropriate equipment to provide optimal care to babies in the SNCU? Are there some SNCU policies/guidelines or regulations you would like to see strengthened? In what ways?
- 2) Can you tell me about the process of obtaining new equipment for the SNCU? What are the steps in this process?
- 3) Who is responsible for budgeting SNCU equipment? Can you procure your own equipment? Ensuring the maintenance of the equipment? Repairing equipment? Do you work with AMCs? What is your opinion of the maintenance service you receive? (Probe for potential bottlenecks in getting equipment)
- 4) What are the challenges of obtaining new equipment? Maintaining equipment?
- 5) How often do SNCU staff experience problems with the SNCU equipment? Which ones are the most troublesome? What are the challenges faced in repairing SNCU equipment?
- 6) Who is responsible for overseeing equipment maintenance issues? Who is responsible for requesting repairs?
- 7) How do you receive feedback from SNCU staff about the SNCU equipment?
- 8) Are the staffing levels adequate to cover patient needs? If not, why? Are SNCU staff skills and experience adequate to address patient needs? If not, why?
- 9) Can you tell me about SNCU staff transfer? (Probe: does this affect quality of care?)
- 10) How are the SNCU staff trained on the SNCU equipment? What are the challenges regarding maintaining a skilled workforce?
- 11) Of the challenges you mentioned, what are the most important? Why?

Facilitators to optimal care

Now I would like to ask you a few questions about what is working well in terms of providing care to babies.

- 12) How is the current suite of SNCU equipment enables the SNCU to provide care to babies? Design (user-friendliness, ease of maintenance); Maintenance (Manuals and trainings (SOPs)
- 13) How are SNCU staff addressing the needs of babies? (Clinical expertise: level of knowledge and skills; Training; Numbers (inventory v. occupancy appropriate); Efficiencies (time management, resources, work flows)
- 14) What is working well at the systems level? (how the SNCU is operated, decision-making regarding procurement, repair and maintenance of equipment, etc.)

Needs and gaps in care

Now I would like to ask you a few questions about the needs and gaps in providing the best care to babies in the SNCU.

- 15) What equipment do you need that you do not currently have? What equipment functions do you need that you do not have? Do you have standby equipment? Equipment components/parts?
- 16) What more needs to be done at the level of staffing to provide the best care for babies in the SNCUs?
 - a. What additional training do staff need? Probe for clinical decision-making, equipment use, time management, work flow
- 17) What are the gaps or needs at the systems level to enable you to provide the best care to babies in the SNCUs?
 - a. What policy changes would enable you to provide the best care to babies in the SNCU?
 - b. What could be done to improve efficiencies in SNCU operations? Probe for clinical staff management, time management, capacity to address faulty equipment, response times for repair or replacement of equipment.

Recommendations to improve care for babies in the SNCUs

- 1) What recommendations do you have for improving care for babies in your SNCU?
- 2) Do you have anything else you would like to add?

Thank you for your participation!